

Entropy and Newton's Second Law

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In this note, we start with classical statistical mechanics for a gas with a potential and argue that $d/dx \ln(d(x)) = F/d(x)$, where $d(x)$ is density. We then try to apply this to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. It can be seen that $d/dx \ln(d(x)) = d/dx \ln(d(x))$ so the idea of entropy seems to appear, although here it is the derivative which is important. Next, we consider the case of changing density with position in quantum mechanics. We try to apply $d/dx \ln(d(x)) = F/d(x)$ which is related to $2 [d/dx W(x)]/W(x)$. The equality only holds for the harmonic oscillator potential. Now $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \sin(px)$ so one also has information about kinetic energy. In fact, one can start with statement related to entropy and obtain a result for kinetic energy in quantum mechanics (for the oscillator). When added to the potential energy, this yields a constant. From this point, one can develop a theory based on this "conservation of energy" or Newton's law which resulted from $d/dx \ln(d(x)) = F/d(x)$ or the derivative of the "information" part of entropy.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

For a sparse gas in a box with a potential, there is a spatial density proportional to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$. In addition, the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is to hold at each point (or in a little box about each point). This seems to imply that it may take some time to verify the distribution really holds as fast particles come into the little box quickly and slow ones a little later. Thus, it is argued that one does not necessarily verify the presence of a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution "instantaneously" or in a short time period. If that is the case, it may also be the case that one does not verify the density instantaneously. In such a situation, one would have to wait and notice how many particles come into a little box at some position per second. This is flux. Thus, in some cases, it may be a flux which determines density. Flux is related to collective velocity from the potential and so density between one box and another may be proportional to $-d/dx V(x)$. In places where collective velocity is high, flux is high, particles arrive quickly and one has the impression of a high density. In places where flux is low (collective velocity low), particles arrive slowly and one has the impression of a low density. The same number of particles will eventually pass through each box, but the amount of time needed will be different. If it takes a long time to measure the presence of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, this long time period is available.

The reason we emphasize the idea of flux is that in quantum mechanics, the change in density seems to be related to a flux:

$d/dx \ln(d(x)) = d/dx \ln(W(x)/W(x)) = 2 W(x) d/dx W(x) / W(x)^2$ where $d/dx W(x)/W(x)$ can be defined as a flux

Note: $[d/dx W(x)]/W(x) = \sum_p p f_p \cos(px)/W$

Classical Statistical Mechanical Density

There are a number of ways to obtain density in classical statistical mechanics, one of the most frequent being the extremization of density subject to constraints. Here we start with the following result (we set mass=1 throughout):

$$dx \frac{d}{dx} d(x) = F(x) dx \quad \text{where } d(x) \text{ is density and } F(x) \text{ force} \quad ((1))$$

For the sake of argument, imagine that this has been found experimentally.

$$\text{In other words:} \quad dx \frac{d}{dx} \ln(d(x)) = F(x) dx = \text{work} = \text{change in kinetic energy} \quad ((2))$$

Thus, the classical work seems to be related to the derivative of "information" given by $\ln(d(x))$ as described by information theory. As a result, it seems that there is a main idea that work changes "information".

One can write $F(x) = -d/dx V(x)$ and so find that

$$d/dx d(x) \text{ is proportional to } [-d/dx V(x)] d(x) \quad ((3))$$

((3)) has probably been discussed in the literature.

This leads to the well-known result: $d(x)$ is proportional to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ where T is a constant at this point. If one knows Newton's law then kinetic energy + $V(x) = E$ so a change in potential energy is equivalent to the negative change in kinetic energy. Thus, this picture can also be dynamic. Thus, ((3)) becomes:

$$d/dx d(x) \text{ is proportional to } d(x) [\text{change in kinetic energy}] \quad ((4))$$

((4)) it seems can be applied to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

$$d [f(v)] \text{ is proportional to } f(v) [\text{change in kinetic energy}]$$

Or $d \ln(f(v)) = \text{change in kinetic energy}$ or

$$f(v) \text{ is proportional to } \exp(-\text{kinetic energy}/T).$$

Thus, the idea that $d[d(x)]$ is proportional to $d(x)$ [change in kinetic energy] seems to apply to statistical mechanics.

Quantum Mechanics

Let us attempt to apply ((4)) to quantum mechanics. One is guaranteed a $d(x)$ whether there is a potential or not. Let us consider the case of a potential. Then:

$$[d/dx d(x)] = [-d/dx V(x)] d(x) \quad \text{with } d(x) = W(x)W(x)$$

$$\text{This gives } 2 [d/dx W(x)]/ W(x) = [-d/dx V(x)]. \quad ((5))$$

In general, ((5)) does not hold in quantum mechanics, but there is one place where it does, namely the harmonic oscillator potential. The result that holds overall in quantum mechanics is:

$$d/dx [.5mv(x)^2] = [-d/dx V(x)] \quad \text{which is Newton's law with the first term written as:}$$

$(-1/2m) [d/dx d/dx W(x)]/ W(x)$. In other words, the time independent Schrodinger equation states that a change in kinetic energy equals work, just as in classical physics. The difference is that quantum mechanics uses an unusual averaging process which may be related to the idea that particles are not points, but undergo zitterbewegung. Thus, a particle without a potential is described by $\sin(px)$ so if the potential scatters such a particle into many states, one might imagine an average kinetic energy given by:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \ (1/2m) p^2 \int \sin^2(px) dx] / W(x). \quad ((6))$$

Let us, however, assume one does not know Newton's law i.e. one only has ((5)). In such a case, there would be no time independent Schrodinger equation or idea of conservation of energy. Imagine that someone one has verified ((5)) for the quantum oscillator. Furthermore, one has the condition: $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ \int \sin^2(px) dx$. In other words one considers a kind of average of strange "sin(px)" objects. Then, the solution of ((5)) which is $\exp(-ax^2)$ also yields the kinetic energy which is given by ((6)). Adding the two gives a constant. In other words, one has obtained conservation of energy, although for one case (the oscillator), by starting with a statement related to the derivative of an information term, namely $\ln(d(x))$. From this point, one could test the conservation of energy statement with the quantum averaging object $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ \int \sin^2(px) dx$ to see that it in fact matches experiment.

In conclusion, it seems one can arrive at conservation of energy in classical physics, by starting with ((4)), a statement about changes in an information term $\ln(d(x))$ and applying it to one case in quantum mechanics (the oscillator) with the rule that $d(x) = W(x)W(x)$ with $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ \int \sin^2(px) dx$. One can show that $d(x) = W(x)W(x)$ if one has a conditional probability $P(p/x) = \int \sin^2(px) dx / W(x)$ (1).

Classical Physics

In classical physics, one has:

$d/dx [d(x) v] = 0$ or $d(x) = C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the velocity and C a constant. ((7))

One may write ((7)) as:

$$d/dx \ln(d(x)) = (-1/v^2) dv/dt \quad ((8))$$

Thus, the derivative of information is again related to $F(x)$ force, but in a different manner.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems one can arrive at conservation of energy in classical physics, by starting with an idea from classical statistical mechanics, namely that:

$$d [\ln(d(x))] = F(x) \quad (\text{with } m=\text{mass}=1 \text{ and } d(x)=W(x)W(x) \quad ((7))$$

and applying it to the quantum mechanical case of an oscillator. In quantum mechanics, one imagines "sin(px)" particles so average kinetic energy is given by:

$$[\text{Sum over } p \ p^2/2m \int \sin^2(px)] / W(x) \text{ where } W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ \int \sin^2(px)$$

Thus, ((7)) yields $W(x)$ from which one can calculate kinetic energy. One can then see that kinetic energy plus potential energy for the oscillator is a constant and generalize this to other cases.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Logarithm of Wavefunction as Partition Function (preprint, zenodo, 2018)